

HEADLESS RELATIVE CLAUSES IN EARLY IRISH

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I. Introduction: aim of the paper and overview

This paper examines the distribution of headless relative clauses in Early Irish, drawing on a collection of relative clauses extracted from *Corpus PalaeoHibernicum*.¹ The label “headless relative clauses” has been applied in the literature² to different kinds of constructions: relative clauses without a nominal head in the matrix clause, including most prominently *wh*-relative clauses without a nominal or pronominal head, e.g. the English and Spanish examples in (1),³ called free headless relative clauses in Caponigro’s survey;⁴ relative clauses with light heads such as isolated determiners, which cannot otherwise occur as phrasal heads,⁵ e.g. the Spanish and the Old Irish examples in (2); and relative clauses without either a nominal head and a relative pronoun or co-referential element in the relative clause, as in the Maltese and Old Irish examples in (3) – termed superfree relative clauses by Caponigro⁶ – where the clause itself denotes a referent.⁷

- 1) a. English
I heard what you said.
- b. Spanish
Tengo con quién hablar.
have.PRS.1SG with whom speak.INF
'I have someone to talk to.'
- c. English
We will do whatever is needed.

1. STIFTER *et alii*, 2021.

2. DRYER, 2013; CAPONIGRO, 2021; COMRIE and KUTEVA, 2013b.

3. Examples are glossed according to the Leipzig Glossing Rules (<https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/pdf/Glossing-Rules.pdf>). Words are separated according to modern editorial practices. Angle brackets are used for segmental pronominal morphemes that occur within the verbal lexeme and backslash is used in the glosses for initial consonantal mutations. Conventionally, conjunct particles, which affect verb stress and require conjunct inflection, have been detached through the symbol separating affixes, while conjunctions which do not trigger stress changes and are followed by verbs with absolute inflection have been detached by the symbol for clitics (=). Case letters are employed at the beginning of Old Irish examples and translations only when reporting the beginning of a gloss or sentence in the original text; the formulaic “i.” which introduces many glosses has been generally omitted.

4. CAPONIGRO, 2021.

5. CITKO, 2004; CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 19-22.

6. CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 22-23; the Maltese example is from SADLER and CAMILLERI, 2018.

7. See DRYER, 2013, sect. 1.

- 2) a. Spanish
Lo que tú crees no es cierto.
 DET.M.SG REL you.SG.SBJ believe.PRS.2SG NEG is true.M.SG
 'What you believe is not true.'
- b. *indaas a ndubeir=som ar thus*
 than DET.NOM.SG.N NREL\put.PRS.3SG=3SG on beginning.DAT
 'than what he puts first' (MI 47a14)
- 3) a. Maltese
Għamil-t li għid-t-l-i.
 do.PFV-1SG COMP say.PFV-2SG-DAT-1SG
 'I did what you told me.'
- b. *ni-mbia durata ind iterum*
 NEG-OBJ.3SG.M\be.FUT.3SG REL\give.SBJV.PRS.3SG in.3SG.ACC.N [LAT]again
 'he won't have anything that he might give for it again' (MI 57a13)

Early Irish does not have any *wh*-relative pronoun and therefore does not have free *wh*-relatives such as those in (1), except for free-choice whatever-relatives introduced by the interrogative pronoun *cip*.⁸ On the other hand, instances such as (3.b) occur in Old Irish, as already noted by Thurneysen,⁹ and will be the focus of this paper. Relative clauses with light heads as in (2.b) and other functional equivalents in Early Irish of headless *wh*-relative clauses, which will be termed here open relative clauses with set antecedents, will also be briefly tackled by way of contrast to headless relative clauses. Note that while Caponigro's survey of headless relative clauses includes all the types listed above, the chapters on relative clauses in the *World Atlas of Language Structures*¹⁰ take into account constructions like (3) but not non-headed *wh*-relatives such as (1).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the corpus, the query and the process which led to the selection of headless relative clauses, and introduces the parameters which will then be detailed and used to classify examples in Section 3. Section 3.1 presents all the examples of headless relative clauses in the corpus and Section 3.2 analyses the data according to the syntactic and semantic parameters set out in Section 2, namely case roles in the relative and in the matrix clause, animacy and referential status. Section 4 briefly compares the distribution of headless relative clauses with the occurrences of similar relative clauses headed by a restricted set of antecedents, in order to complement the description in Section 3. Section 5 summarises the results and concludes the paper.

8. The greater cross-linguistic tendency for indefinites that express free-choice to be interrogative-based is noted in HASPELMATH, 2013.

9. THURNEYSEN, 1946, p. 315-316.

10. DRYER, 2013; COMRIE and KUTEVA, 2013b.

II. Database and methodology

The database used for this survey relies on *Corpus PalaeoHibernicum* (*CorPH*).¹¹ *CorPH* is a freely available and searchable lexicographic database, which gathers at present 76 deeply annotated Old and Middle Irish texts. Out of a search in *CorPH* which extracted all textual units including a relative clause (search no. 4447),¹² headless relative clauses and open relative clauses with set antecedents, i.e. relative clauses without any nominal head or with the pronominal heads listed in (4), have been extracted manually.

- 4) *a* (*n-*) ‘the’, *cách* ‘everyone’, *cach óen* ‘everyone’, *cip hé* ‘whoever’, *intí* (*antí*) ‘that one (thing)’, *nech* (*ní*) ‘any (one, thing)’, *nach óen* ‘anyone’, *nanní* ‘anything’, *sechi(p)* + stressed pronoun ‘who/whatever’

The search results of the original query were 5080 relative verb forms contained in textual units from 34 different texts. These include the *Annals of Ulster*, *Baile Chuinn*, the *Poems of Blathmac*, the *Milan Glosses*, the *St. Gall Glosses* and other glosses on Priscian, the *Turin Glosses on Mark*, the *Armagh Glosses* and many other minor glosses gathered in the *Thesaurus Palaeohibernicus*, and *Monastery of Tallaght*. For the full list of texts, their manuscript sources, editions and dating, I refer to the list of texts in *CorPH* and in the search results (see footnote 12): note that all Early Irish examples quoted in this paper rely on the online edition. Among the automatically extracted relative verbs, 537 open relative clauses were manually selected. Briefly, the selection criteria were: a) exclude all relative verb forms that do not match the definition of relative clause, that is “A construction is considered a relative clause... if it is a clause which, either alone or in combination with a noun, denotes something and if the thing denoted has a semantic role within the relative clause” (Dryer¹³); b) exclude all relative clauses with full NP heads; c) exclude relative clauses that occur right at the beginning of a gloss and can have a nominal antecedent in the Latin text. Criterion a) is meant to keep apart in particular complement clauses, which in Early Irish can assume the same morphological marking as relative clauses (see GOI,¹⁴ where Thurneysen notes that “In such constructions they are no longer relative clauses in the strict sense”).

The 537 clauses that form the database of this survey belong to 15 different texts (*Armagh Glosses*, *Baile Chuinn*, *Milan Glosses*, *St. Gall* and *Karlsruhe Priscian Glosses*, *Turin Glosses on Mark*, *Poems of Blathmac*, *Bern Servius*, *Karlsruhe Augustine*, *Karlsruhe Bede*, *Laon Cassiodorus*, *Munich Paul Commentary*, *Vatican Psalter*

11. STIFTER *et alii*, 2021.

12. The search results are retrievable, as all *CorPH* search results are, at <https://chronhib.maynoothuniversity.ie/chronhibWebsite/tables?page=0&limit=10000&fprop=&fval=&dtable=search&ctable=&search=true&id=4447>. Among the 78 texts listed in *CorPH*, the *Epistle of Jesus* and *Cáin Domnaig* have not been captured yet (as of June 2023). Note that both the automatic search and the manual selection may have overlooked examples, but the database is wide enough to grant representativity.

13. DRYER, 2013, sect. 1; see also CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 51.

14. THURNEYSEN, 1946, p. 318.

Commentary, Vienna Bede, Monastery of Tallaght). Among these, 26 headless relative clauses of the type in (3.b) above – including a few doubtful cases – have been detected. Each of these instances will be discussed in detail in Section 3.

The parameters used in Section 3.2 to describe their distribution are:

- syntax: case-roles of the non-overt head Noun Phrase admitted in the matrix and in the relative clause, and their relationship (subject/nominative, object/accusative, prepositional, genitive)
- semantics: animacy (animate/human vs. inanimate, cf. English *who/what*) and referential status of the Noun Phrase which includes the relative clause, with related inferences (definite-active, indefinite specific and indefinite non-specific, only partially corresponding to maximal, free-choice and existential free relative clauses respectively in Caponigro’s classification)
- lexicon: pronominal heads, if any, admitted in relation to the syntactic and semantic parameters (relevant for open relative clauses with set antecedents)

These parameters try to set apart the various features taken into account for the classification of headless relative clauses in the recent cross-linguistic survey by Caponigro¹⁵ and will be detailed below in Section 3.2. The analysis will not take into account the relativisation strategy (e.g. initial mutation, relative ending, relative particle with prepositions) since that depends on the verbs and on the case-roles, while its distribution does not show any relevant difference as opposed to fully headed relative clauses.

III. Headless relative clauses in *CorPH*

List of examples

In this subsection I will present all the instances of headless relative clauses extracted from *CorPH*, listed in (5-27), and in subsection 3.2 I will comment on their features according to the syntactic and semantic parameters set down in Section 2. First the clearest examples are given (5-22), to which (3.b) also belongs, then instances for which other interpretations are possible (23-24) and doubtful cases (25-27) are presented.

5)	<i>as</i>	<i>tormach</i>	<i>hí</i>	<i>tintud</i>	<i>septien</i>	<i>is</i>	<i>tormach</i>	<i>són</i>
	COP.PRS.3SG.REL	addition.NOM	in	version.DAT	Septuagint.GEN	COP.PRS.3SG	addition.NOM	that
	<i>dano</i>	<i>hí</i>	<i>tintud</i>	<i>teothis</i>				
	then	in	version	Theodotio.GEN				

‘What is an addition in the translation of the Septuagint, that is also an addition in the translation of Theodotio’
(M1 2a15)

15. CAPONIGRO, 2021.

As noted by Griffith,¹⁶ the emendation *anastomarch* in *Thes.*¹⁷ is unnecessary in (5).

- 6) *amal as=n-ed as moam serc lin=nai*
 like COP.PRS.3SG.REL=REL-3SG.NOM.N COP.PRS.3SG.REL biggest love.NOM for.1PL=1PL
adchotadsam tri-ar saithar sain-diles síc is=ed
 REL.obtain.PRF.1PL through-our work.ACC proper-own.ACC [LAT]so COP.PRS.3SG=3SG.NOM.N
as moam serc la dia maicc israhél
 COP.PRS.3SG.REL biggest love.NOM for God.ACC son.NOM.PL Israel.GEN
frissa-rusaithraigestar oc a tuididen di cech imniud
 towards.REL-work.PRF.3SG at their lead.VN.DAT from every trouble.DAT
 ‘As what we have most love for is what we have obtained through our own labour, so what God has most love for are the Children of Israel, for whom he has laboured leading them from every trouble’ (MI 92c5)
- 7) *is inunn dia-teit le=som an ioseph*
 COP.PRS.3SG same.NOM to.REL-go.PRS.3SG for.3SG=3SG DET.NOM.SG.N Joseph
 7 *an effraim*
 and DET.NOM.SG.N Ephraim
 ‘that to which *Joseph* and *Ephraim* apply is the same according to him’ (MI 100b9)
- 8) *fo-theistib .i. forsa-moith cath són daig*
 down-poured.DAT.PL i.e. on.REL-break.PRS.3SG battle.NOM PRON.NOM.SG.N seek.PRS.3SG
loc ñ dia ditin
 place.ACC ACC for.his protection.DAT
 ‘poured down, i.e. he who is defeated in battle seeks a place for his protection’ (MI 110d10)

Again, in (8) *Thes.* suggests to supply *intí* before *forsamoith*, but Griffith notes that this is unnecessary.¹⁸

- 9) *int-í nad tabair digail is*
 DET.NOM.SG.M-DEICT NEG.REL give.PRS.3SG punishment.ACC COP.PRS.3SG
nach fitir side
 NEG.REL.OBJ.3SG.N find_out.PST.3SG 3SG.NOM.M
 ‘He who does not inflict punishment, he is someone who does not know it’ (MI 91a20)

I adopt here for (9) the syntactic interpretation given by Griffith and taken up in *CorPH*:¹⁹ *intí nad-tabair digail* is a nominativus pendens phrase containing a relative clause, while *nach-fitir*, a headless relative clause, is the predicate of the main copular clause and *side* is the subject of the copular clause, resuming the nominativus pendens. This interpretation does not correspond to the translation in *Thes.*,²⁰ namely ‘he who does not inflict punishment, it is that he knows it not’, but it is firmly based on the sense of the Latin text of which it represents a gloss – *quomodo scit si*

16. GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013.

17. STOKES and STRACHAN, 1901, p. 7.

18. GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013; STIFTER *et alii*, 2021.

19. GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013; STIFTER *et alii*, 2021.

20. STOKES and STRACHAN, 1901.

- 13) *adchos*[a]ire .i. *adchois* *maldacht* *in* *popoil* *foir*
 averter.NOM i.e. REL\avert.PRS.3SG curse.ACC DET.GEN.SG.M people.GEN on.3SG.M
 ‘an averter, i.e. one who averts on himself the curse of the people’

(Turin Glosses, *Thes.* I 492, 111)

- 14) 7 *ni* *cian* *huaib* *i* *mbát*
 and NEG long.NOM.N from.2PL in REL\be.PRS.HAB.3PL
 ‘and it is not far from you where they are usually’ (Monastery of Tallaght)²⁵

The following instances (15-19) group cases of imprecations, curses and beatitudes, where the headless relative clause depends on *mairc* ‘woe, alas’ or *céin-mair* ‘happy’; it therefore occurs where a head noun in the accusative (or in the dative preceded by *do*) vs. in the nominative, accusative or dative would be expected respectively. The construction with a relative clause is explicitly noted in *eDIL*²⁶ for *mairc* (s.v. *mairg*, *mairc*, “c. with omission of subst., its place being taken by a rel. sent.”) and also figures in the first example reported in *eDIL* for *céin-mair*, viz. *céinmair noda-aínsed* ‘happy he who should spare him’ (*Togail Bruidne Da Derga* 111, *eDIL* s.v. *maraid*, I b). All instances in *CorPH* happen to be in poetry; (16) and (17) contain two relative clauses each.

- 15) *Mairg* *adchondairc* *mac* *Dé* *bí*
 woe REL\see.PRF.3SG son.ACC God.GEN alive.GEN.M
fri *croich* *in-a* *glóeth-rigi*
 against cross.ACC in-his glue-stretch.VN.DAT
 ‘Woe to anyone who has seen the son of the living God stretched fast to the cross.’

(Poems of Blathmac 481-82)

- 16) *Mairc* *rochar* *mac* *ríg* *nime*
 woe REL\love.PRF.3SG son.ACC king.GEN sky.GEN
adchondairc *a* *chró-lige*
 REL\see.PRF.3SG his M\blood-lie.VN.ACC
 ‘Alas for the one who has come to love the son of the King of Heaven, who has seen him lying in gore’

(Poems of Blathmac 529-30)

- 17) *Céin-mair* *ro<d>creiti,* *ro<d>car*
 long-live PRF<OBJ.3SG.M.REL>believe.PRF.3SG PRF<OBJ.3SG.M.REL>love.PRF.3SG
in *coimdiu* *rocofsemmar*
 DET.NOM.SG.M lord.NOM lament.PRF.1PL.REL
 ‘Happy who has believed him, who has come to love him, the Lord we have keened’

(Poems of Blathmac 533-34)

25. Text unit ID in *CorPH* S0070-398.

26. *eDIL* 2019.

- 18) *Céin-mair* *rochúalae* *clais* *cóir*
 long-live REL\believe.PRF.3SG assembly.ACC choir.GEN
síl *n-Ádaim* *im-a* *senóir*
 seed.ACC ACC-Adam.GEN around-its ancestor.ACC
 ‘Happy who has heard the choir assembly, Adam’s seed around their ancestor’
 (Poems of Blathmac 725-26)

- 19) *Scarfaid –* *mairg* *nád-ais* *a* *thnú–*
 separate.FUT.3SG woe NEG.REL-fear.PRS.3SG his M\envy.ACC
caíreha *gela* *fri* *mindu*
 sheep.PL.ACC white.PL.ACC against lamb.PL.ACC
 ‘He will separate – woe to who does not fear him – white sheep from lambs.’
 (Poems of Blathmac 1067-68)

A case which is similar to (15-19) is (20), where the main clause also apparently consists of a nominal predicate. Although *CorPH* gives the translation I report below and analyses *bebais* as a relative verbal form, other interpretations are possible; for instance, Murphy²⁷ includes in the sentence the previous words *bess tress* and translates ‘perhaps in the third month over a year he shall die by the sea.’

- 20) *mi* *for bliadni* *bebais* *muir*
 month.NOM on year.DAT die.FUT.3SG.REL sea.DAT
 ‘a month and a year (for the one) who will die in the sea’ (Baile Chuinn)²⁸

In (21), (22) and (23) the same copular predicate *sain* ‘else, different’ occurs in the main clause. In this predicate lies an ambiguity, as it can either be used as an adjectival or as an adverbial predicate, and the phrase denoting the standard (something to which something else is different) can either be introduced by *ocus* or be a prepositional phrase with *fri*. In (21) *dofoirnde* clearly has a direct relative clause marker (i.e. lenition) and is translated with a headless *wh*-relative clause both in *Thes.* and in Bauer *et al.*²⁹ (22) is probably another genuine instance, but it could also be seen in two ways, similarly to (23). In fact (23) can be interpreted as having two conjoined subjects with two slightly different structures (‘A and B are different’), but also as having an adverbial predicate and cleft structure (so *Thes.* ‘differently is it shown *sensibus* and as it is afterwards’), therefore without assuming a headless relative clause in *donadbantar sensibus*.

- 21) *is* *sain* *dofoirnde* *són fri-sin* *roithnigud*
 COP.PRS.3SG different.NOM.N REL\signify.PRS.3SG that against-DET.ACC.SC.M shining.ACC
 ‘what that [scil. Λευκοθέα] signifies is different from the radiance’ (Sg 36a3)

27. MURPHY, 1952, p. 149, does not consider *bebais* a relative form but a Middle Irish form for *bebaid* (footnote 11).

28. Text ID in *CorPH* S0003-29.

29. BAUER *et al.*, 2017.

In (25) and (26) below the ambiguity lies in the structure of the glosses: in (25) the *et ceteras* make the syntax of the gloss uneven. *Operibus* could in principle be the head noun of the relative verb *durigni*, as it heads all the phrases listed afterwards; I assume this interpretation is what gives the translation ‘which he had done’ in Griffith and Stifter³³ and *CorPH*. In (26) again the head noun could be the Latin word *facto* (‘the deed that Achitofel had done’). Note that it is not uncommon to find in the glosses relative clauses that have antecedents in the main Latin text; therefore, gloss-initial clauses that may have antecedents in the Latin text have not been taken into account, as stated in Section 2. The relative clauses can also be separated from the head by “.i.”, either at the beginning or within the gloss.

25)	<i>operibus</i>	.i.	<i>dia</i>	<i>sonartnugud</i>	<i>di</i>	<i>anechtair</i>
	[LAT]work.PL.DAT	i.e.	to.ils ³⁴	strengthen.VN.DAT	from	outside
	.i. <i>sliab</i>	<i>sión</i>	<i>di</i>	<i>andes</i>	rl.	7
	i.e. mount.NOM	Zion	from	south	etc.	and
	<i>durigni</i>	<i>dia</i>	<i>soirad</i>	.i.	<i>slige</i>	<i>assar</i>
	REL\do.PRF.3SG	to.their	save.VN.DAT	i.e.	slay.VN.NOM	Assyrian.PL.GEN
						etc

‘from the deeds, i.e. to strengthen it from outside, namely, Mount Zion on the south etc., and what he had done for their deliverance, namely, the smiting of the Assyrians etc.’ (M1 67d2)

26)	<i>facto</i>	.i.	<i>dorigni</i>	<i>achitofel</i>
	fact.ABL ³⁵	i.e.	REL\do.PRF.3SG	Achitofel
	‘fact, i.e. what Achitofel had done’			
				(M1 23b11)

Finally, (27) contains an instance of what is likely to be a petrified construction with a headless relative clause, the expression *is/ba arafia (do)* ‘is/was in (one’s) power’, already analysed as such in Pedersen’s Grammar.³⁶ Pedersen translated the idiom as ‘es ist (ein Ding), das vorhanden sein wird’, and pointed to the same construction as M1 91a20 (here 9), in the analysis suggested by Griffith and accepted here.

27)	<i>is</i>	<i>ar<a>fia</i>	<i>dom</i>
	COP.PRS.3SG	on<REL>be.FUT.3SG	to.1SG
	‘I have in my power’, lit. ‘it is something that will impend on me’		
			(Vatican Psalter Commentary, <i>Thes.</i> 1, 3, 4a)

33. GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013.

34. I stick here to the analysis by GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013 (in *CorPH* it is missing), but the possessive pronoun *a* is co-referent with *civitate*, so possibly a feminine possessive. Since the gloss is on the following Latin text: *ex his quæ in ciuitate operatus est, magnus [deus] apparuit*, the preposition in *dia* could be *de*, rather than *do*, translating Latin *ex*, which governs *operibus* (therefore, ‘from its fortification’, ‘from the fact that he fortified’).

35. This is part of an ablative absolute in the Latin text (*quo audito*).

36. PEDERSEN, 1909, vol. i, p. 272.

Classification and distribution of instances

In the following analysis I will take into account only the instances of headless relative clauses that have been considered sure enough in the presentation above in 3.1, i.e. (3.b), (5)-(22). In Table 1 I present in chart form the values of the basic syntactic and semantic parameters set down in Section 2. The instances where two conjoined relative verb forms occur in the same complex sentence, i.e. (16) and (17), have been considered only once, as they represent instances of the same values for all these parameters. Cases are used, viz. nominative and accusative, instead of syntactic relations, whenever there is no direct syntactic relationship of the relative clause to a main predicate (e.g. a *nominativus pendens* construction, a nominal sentence or gloss).

Concerning the referential status of the entity denoted by the relative clause, the three statuses, definite-active, indefinite specific and indefinite non-specific, are distinguished according to the following criteria. The referent is definite and active in discourse if it has a unique referent already established or identifiable in the text (including of course the Latin text for the glosses); the referent denoted by the relative clause may be anaphorically resumed. The referent is indefinite specific if it does not have a well-established co-referent element in the text, but it is liable to be resumed. It is indefinite non-specific if it occurs after an existential predicate, as set out in Caponigro³⁷ for so-called existential free relative clauses, and it is not liable to be resumed (see Haspelmath 1997³⁸ about non-specificity and referentiality). It should be noted that this classification groups universal interpretation with indefinites, in contexts which can be paraphrased with expressions such as ‘anyone, everyone who’ (such as for example in (13), (15), (16) and (17)), while Caponigro’s classification rather assimilates free-choice universal interpretation, as in (1.c), with definites, as in (1.a).³⁹

ex. no.	syntactic role (relative clause)	syntactic role in the matrix clause	animacy	referential status
3	object	subject	inanimate	indefinite non-specific (existential after negative)
5	subject	nominative	inanimate	definite-active (cataphoric)
6	object	subject	inanimate	definite-active (anaphoric)
7	prepositional	subject	inanimate	definite-active
8	prepositional	subject	animate	indefinite specific (resumed)
9	subject	nominative	animate	indefinite specific
10	subject	subject	inanimate	indefinite non-specific (existential after negative)
11	object	subject	inanimate	indefinite non-specific (existential after negation)
12	subject	object	inanimate	indefinite specific

37. CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 14. See examples (3), (10) (11) here.

38. HASPELMATH, 1997, p. 38.

39. CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 16; HASPELMATH, 1997, p. 46.

ex. no.	syntactic role (relative clause)	syntactic role in the matrix clause	animacy	referential status
13	subject	nominative	animate	indefinite specific
14	prepositional	subject	inanimate (location)	definite-active
15	subject	accusative (after <i>mair</i>)	animate	indefinite specific
16	subject	accusative (after <i>mair</i>)	animate	indefinite specific
17	subject	nominative/accusative (after <i>céinmair</i>) ⁴⁰	animate	indefinite specific
18	subject	nominative/accusative (after <i>céinmair</i>)	animate	indefinite specific
19	subject	accusative (after <i>mair</i>)	animate	indefinite specific
20	subject	?	animate	definite (?)
21	object	subject	inanimate	definite-active
22	prepositional	subject	inanimate	definite-active

TABLE 1. Syntactic roles, animacy and referential status associated with headless relative clauses

From the point of view of syntactic roles, all functions appear to be admitted except genitive, which is notoriously a position rarely relativised in Old Irish,⁴¹ but for which examples outside the corpus might be traced (a Middle Irish instance from poetry is quoted by Roma⁴²). The only function that appears to be barred from headless relative clauses in Early Irish is prepositional complement in the matrix clause:⁴³ if the syntactic role in the matrix clause is governed by a preposition, a pronominal head such as *nech*, *ní* or *intí* surfaces (see Section 4).

Moreover, there is no restriction regarding the relationship between the syntactic function in the relative vs. in the matrix clause, such as for example the matching issue set out in Citko,⁴⁴ who argues that in Polish the relative pronoun in headless relative clauses must fulfill the category and case requirements of both the matrix and the relative clause. Rather, in most instances, the syntactic roles in the matrix and in the relative clause do not match. Syntactically, therefore, headless relative clauses appear to be almost free variants of open relative clauses with set antecedents.

The referent denoted by the relative clause can be either animate or inanimate (roughly corresponding to English *who/what* respectively): the interpretation relies on

40. Although in principle *céinmair*, containing a verbal form, is expected to be followed by the nominative case, the noun phrase that occurs after *céinmair* in the following quatrain, namely *cech ndúil* (see (29) below), is clearly in the accusative case, so accusative is probably the right case here. The accusative after *céinmair* also occurs at Balthmac 1052 (*céinmair... cach nóen*).

41. See ROMA, 2007.

42. ROMA, 2007, p. 254, ex. (25). Further instances are quoted by Ó CATHASAIGH, 1990.

43. What looks closest to an instance of a headless relative clause with prepositional role both in the matrix and in the relative clause is (24). (25) could also be an instance if the analysis in footnote 34 is correct. Other possible instances of prepositional relative clauses whose head is a pronominal prepositional complement are quoted by Ó CATHASAIGH, 1990, p. 419, footnote 3.

44. CITKO, 2004.

the context, notably on the semantics of the predicate in the relative clause.⁴⁵ It can also have different referential statuses, encompassing a larger set of possibilities than English *who/what*. It admits definite interpretation (cp. the English example in (1.a) above), as is clearly the case in (5), (7) and (21) and possibly also (22) – (23) if it is a genuine example. In fact, it also admits indefinite non-specific semantics, with main clause negative existential predicates, as in (3), (10) and (11), which is not allowed for English headless *wh*-relatives.

IV. Comparison with open relative clauses with set antecedents

In this section I can only sketch a few observations about competing constructions that may be compared with headless relative clauses, namely relative clauses with set antecedents, which are listed in (4).

As already noted above in the comments to (5) and (8) (Section 3.1), in some cases editors have suggested to supply a determiner head before the relative verb, namely *a* (*n*-), a form which corresponds to the neuter article and which holds for nominative and accusative inanimates,⁴⁶ or *intí* (viz. all its inflected forms), the definite article supplemented by the invariable deictic particle *-í*, a form which is mainly used as a relative clause head. While it is certainly possible that *a* (*n*-) was inadvertently omitted, the number of examples of headless relative clauses where this cannot be the case guarantees that such emendations are unnecessary. Examples where it is not possible to supply such a head include poetry, for metrical reasons, but also instances with negative existential predicates in the main clause, since *a* (*n*-) (and *intí/antí*) cannot be indefinite non-specific (see (3), (10) and (11) above).

The relative clause head *a n*- (headword *a*⁴ in *eDIL*) occurs in 37 instances in the corpus of 537 open relative clauses considered here, while *intí/antí* is much more frequent and occurs 274 times with a relative clause.⁴⁷ It appears to be the most frequent

45. Other semantic features usually taken into account in describing headless relative clauses (e.g. place *where*, time *when*, manner *how*) are usually expressed in Old Irish through an accompanying head noun, such as *dú*, *maigen* ‘place’, *tain* ‘time’, *cruth* ‘form’. Relative clauses introduced by the preposition *i* ‘in’ can however mean ‘(the place) where’, see (14) above.

46. There is one instance in *Monastery of Tallaght* where the form *and* appears to occur as a genitival form, namely *ar comalnad and ro-tairrngert do anmcharait* ‘on fulfillment of what he had promised to the confessor’ (Text unit ID S0070-309). In the Würzburg Glosses there are two further examples that confirm that *a n*- may occur where a genitive is expected: 27a10 *nebchretem anadiadar dicrist* ‘not to believe what is declared of Christ’ and 30a8 *ismó afius deitsiu andorigeni di maith frimsa* ‘you know better what good he has done to me’.

47. All the instances where *a n*- and *antí* followed by the relative form of the copula introduce a quotation (e.g. Ml 37a18 *in son file iar cul indí as sanctis* ‘the word which is behind *sanctis*’) have not been included in the database of open relative clauses (see BREATNACH 1990 about this usage). However, a few structurally similar instances, where they are not only semantically void fillers but referential elements, have been included, e.g. Sg 39a20 and 21, where *indí as superior* and *indí as inferior* are glosses on *superioris* and *inferioris* respectively. According to *CorPH*, among the 891 occurrences of *intí* in the corpus, 501 are followed by a relative clause (465 labelled as “antecedent of a relative clause” and 36 as “in grammaticalized conjunction”, e.g. *arindí*, *isindí*;

head of open relative clauses, it can express any case-role and animacy feature and can have either definite or indefinite specific interpretation.

In a few instances, open relative clauses with set heads alternate with headless relative clauses: the couplets following (16) and (17) in the same quatrain, reported in (28) and (29) respectively, show *cách* and *cech* + noun with similar syntax and semantics.

28)	<i>Cíth</i>	<i>cách</i>	<i>rochóalae</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>chlú</i>
	even	every.NOM	REL\hear.PRF.3SG	his	M\ fame.ACC
	<i>for<da>tá</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>bíth-chuíníu.</i>		
	on<OBJ.3PL>be.PRS.3SG	his	ever-weep.VN.NOM		
	‘Even everyone who has heard his fame, it is incumbent upon them to keen him perpetually’				
	(Poems of Blathmac, 531-32)				

29)	<i>Céin-mair</i>	<i>cech</i>	<i>ndúil</i>	<i>ad<id>cí</i>
	long-live	every	ACC\creature.ACC	<OBJ.3SG.M>see.PRS.3SG
	<i>i mbíth-<i>flaith</i></i>	<i>co</i>	<i>mbíth sláini</i>	
	in eternal-kingdom.DAT	with	eternal-salvation.DAT	
	‘Happy every creature who sees him in the eternal kingdom with eternal salvation’			
	(Poems of Blathmac, 535-36)			

Differently from *a n-*, and in addition to *intí/antí*, which however mostly occurs before a relative clause, the other frequent set antecedents *nech/ní* ‘someone, something’ and *cách* ‘everyone’ (only animate) may all be used without a following relative clause. The alternatives *cach óen* and *in cach* are also only animate: the head *cech/cach óen* only occurs in the Milan Glosses (once, Ml 22b1) and in Bern Servius (*Thes.* II, 235.117a), with specific indefinite meaning as defined in Section 3.2. The head *nach óen* (‘everyone’) in *Monastery of Tallaght* seems to be synonymous both with earlier *intí* ‘anyone, everyone who’ and to *cách* and *cách óen* (always animate) in the Milan Glosses and in the *Poems of Blathmac*.⁴⁸

The head *nach óen* with an open relative clause again only occurs in Ml (once, 107a15) and *Monastery of Tallaght* (4 instances), while *in cách* only in the St. Gall Glosses (2 instances at 188a31) and *Monastery of Tallaght* (3 instances). The combination *na(n) ní* for the corresponding inanimates only occurs in Ml, where it is frequently resumed, as in (30) below. The neuter form *ní* may occur in negative clauses (18 instances out of 82) and with comparatives or superlatives as predicates in the following relative clause (12 occurrences).

data extracted from search no. 5002 <https://chronhib.maynoothuniversity.ie/chronhibWebsite/tables?page=0&limit=0&fprop=&fval=&dtable=search&ctable=&search=true&id=5002>). A thorough investigation and description of the functions of a *n-* and *intí/antí* is beyond the scope of this paper, but I refer to GARCÍA CASTILLERO, 2018, 2023 for detailed corpus-driven studies.

48. There is only one instance in the corpus where *cacha* clearly has indefinite non-specific meaning (with indifference inference as in *whoever*), namely Sg 12b7 *cosmail leiss cacha orr im cara fá aescare* ‘the same for him whichever he kills, whether friend or foe’. However *cacha* appears to be an interrogative conjunct particle here, see THURNEYSSEN, 1946, p. 289; this is the only instance in *CorPH*.

(30)	<i>na-<i>nní</i></i>	<i>frisoirc</i>		<i>doib</i>
	any-thing	REL/offend.PRS.3SG		to.3PL.DAT
	<i>f<a>scannat</i>	<i>hua</i>	<i>adarcuib</i>	
	<OBJ.3SG.N>toss.PRS.3PL	from.their	horn.PL.DAT	
	'anything which offends them, they toss it with their horns' (Ml 63b17)			

Genitive role in the relative clause is only attested with *intí*, while genitive role in the main clause (64 instances) occurs with the following heads: *intí*, *nech/ní*, *cech óen* (once in Ml 22b1), *in cách* (only in *Monastery of Tallaght*, three occurrences).⁴⁹

The phrase *cip hé* as a relative clause head is found in the corpus only in three occurrences in the Milan Glosses and with a following noun once in *Monastery of Tallaght*: it is always inanimate and has indefinite non-specific meaning, in particular free-choice with indifference inference ('whatever, whichever'). A similar meaning has *sechi(p)* + stressed pronoun, a free-choice indefinite that is mainly used absolutely, i.e. without introducing a relative clause, a feature that is common cross-linguistically for free-choice elements such as English *who/whatever* as noted by Caponigro;⁵⁰ with a following relative clause it occurs in the corpus in 12 instances, only in the Milan and St. Gall glosses, and is attested with any stressed pronoun (masculine, feminine, neuter and plural). The forms *cip hé* and *sechip* contain a subjunctive morpheme, again a recurrent cross-linguistic feature of indefinite lexemes with the aforementioned meaning.⁵¹

Finally, it might be worth mentioning two code-switching instances where *intí* is followed by a Latin relative clause introduced by the Latin relative pronoun *qui*, (31) and (32), in contrast to an instance of a cleft sentence (33), where the Latin verb which occurs where in Irish a relative verb form would be expected is not preceded by a relative pronoun. In both (31) and (32) the relative clause represents a quotation from a relative clause in the Latin glossed text, while this is not the case in (33). This contrast, together with the code-switching contexts in (9), (11) and (12),⁵² where Irish headless relative clauses correspond to Latin non-headed relative clauses introduced by *qui*, suggests that Irish relative verb forms were assimilated to Latin relative pronoun + verb only when they represented noun phrases, and not in cleft sentences.⁵³

49. See footnote 46 about an example with *a n-* in the corpus.

50. CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 18-19.

51. CAPONIGRO, 2021, p. 17.

52. See the comments above in Section 3.1 and footnote 24 about the Latin contexts.

53. Similar switching contexts as (33), i.e. mixed Irish and Latin cleft sentences, also occur in the Würzburg Glosses with Latin non-relative clauses, e.g. Wb 9b19, 10a1, discussed by BISAGNI 2014, p. 45-46. Bisagni's suggestions about the motivations that lie behind this structure (mismatch between Old Irish and Latin both on the functional/semantic and on the morpho-syntactic level) are entirely acceptable to me. I am grateful to an anonymous reviewer for pointing out these instances to me.

- 31) *lase* *dufuinchidet* *ind-hí*
 when REL\depart.PRS.3PL.⁵⁴ DET.NOM.PL.M-DEICT
dano *quos* *solet* *experiri* *aduersitas*
 then [LAT]PRON.REL.ACC.PL.M [LAT]is_wont.PRS.3SG [LAT]prove.INF [LAT]adversity.NOM
 ‘when those, then, whom adversity usually tests depart’ (MI 108b4)
- 32) *hit* *hé* *do<d>mainetar* *insin*
 COP.PRS.3PL 3PL <OBJ.3SG.N.REL>think.PRS.3PL that
ind-í *qui* *reliqua*
 DET.NOM.PL.M-DEICT [LAT]PRON.REL.NOM.PL.M [LAT]etcetera
 ‘it is they who think that, those who etc.’ (Sg 5a6)
- 33) *conid* *in* *spirit* *adamre*
 so_that.COP.PRS.3SG DET.NOM.SG.M spirit.NOM wondrous.NOM
tra *profetauit* *post* *passionem*
 then [LAT]prophecy.PRF.3SG [LAT]after [LAT]passion.ACC
 ‘so that it is the marvelous spirit that prophesied after the passion’
 (Armagh Glosses, *Thes.* I, 495, 170b1)

V. Conclusions and prospects

Although the overview presented in this paper would likely benefit from a complement survey of headless relative clauses in the Würzburg Glosses, which as yet do not enjoy the ease of sifting allowed by an annotated database,⁵⁵ the data gathered through *CorPH* are large enough to show that headless relative clauses are quantitatively marginal but well-established constructions in Early Irish grammar. Even petrified periphrases appear to stem from headless relative constructions (see (27) above). Their occurrence is rather unrestricted from the syntactic point of view, as the only barred syntactic roles in the corpus are prepositional complement in the matrix clause and genitive in either clauses. Conditions in the relationship between syntactic role in the

54. The meaning of this verb should rather be ‘depart, separate’ (as in *Thes.*) than ‘descend’ (as in GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013 and *CorPH*, with a question mark), as its explanation with *etiscarid* at MI 67b4 suggests. The context is similar in both loci and in both cases where it occurs the Latin verb it renders is **discendo* (*discendendo*, *discidunt*), but this should rather be emended to forms of *discedo*.

55. A preliminary survey has given the following results: 4 sure instances of headless relative clauses are attested in the Würzburg Glosses, where the syntactic role in the relative clause is mainly subject and once object, and in the main clause only subject: 18a2 *nicon fil bas sciúth lim actrop ar crist* ‘there is nothing which irks me, provided that it be for Christ’, 23c21 *rafitis as lia* ‘(what are) most know it’, 32a13 *bieid bes ferr de tra* ‘there will be something better therefrom then’, 32a22 *attá immurgu asbéer* ‘there is however something that I will say’. A couple of less sure instances have the same case role in the main and in the relative clause: 8d20 *ishé didiu intectaire maith condaig indobáil dia thigerni* et non sibi ipsi ‘he, then, is the good messenger who seeks glory for his lord and not for himself’, which has cleft-like structure, and 17b6 *ni irbágam nádernam iarríchte ní barscéuil si* ‘we do not boast what we cannot do after arriving...’, or ‘after tidings of you reach (us)?’. Both animate and inanimate, indefinite specific, non-specific and possibly active referents occur.

matrix vs. the relative clause rather point to preference for disjoint case marking, i.e. different cases in matrix and relative clause, but same case is also allowed. The preference could be linked rather to the gapping strategy (i.e. absence of relative pronoun and of overt case-marking in the relative clause) than to head omission conditions.⁵⁶ From the semantic point of view, headless relative clauses in Early Irish can imply animate or inanimate semantics. They can be definite referential, indefinite specific – especially in the universal interpretation with animates – and indefinite non-specific, similarly to non-finite, participial relative clauses in other languages.

To sum up, headless relative clauses in Early Irish appear to be rather free alternatives to headed relative clauses, in particular to open relative clauses with set antecedents such as *a n-*, *intí/aní*, *cách*, *nech/ní*, *nanní*. It could even be argued that headless relative clauses are the basic type of relative clauses in Old Irish and that relative clauses with a nominal head can be analysed as nominal expressions in apposition to the head.⁵⁷ This view cannot be pursued here, but the distribution of definite articles with nouns modified by a relative clause,⁵⁸ together with the widespread use of relative verb forms in complement clauses (GOI⁵⁹ and Section 2 above), seems to comply with this analysis. Be that as it may, headless relative clauses in Early Irish are a typologically remarkable feature given that the language does not have any relative pronoun (either *wh-* or other).

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56. See COMRIE and KUTEVA, 2013a, sect. 3.

57. See DRYER, 2013, sect. 1 for this possibility.

58. ROMA, 2009, 2014.

59. THURNEYSSEN, 1946, p. 318.

REFERENCES

- BAUER *et al.*, 2017: Bernhard BAUER, Rijcklof HOFMAN, Pádraic MORAN, *St Gall Priscian Glosses, version 2.0*, 2017, online at <http://www.stgallpriscian.ie/>.
- BISAGNI, 2014: Jacopo BISAGNI, « Prolegomena to the study of code-switching in the Old Irish Glosses », *Peritia*, 24-25, p. 1-58.
- BREATNACH, 1990: Liam BREATNACH, « On the citation of words and a use of the neuter article in Old Irish », *Ériu*, 41, p. 95-101.
- CAPONIGRO, 2021: Ivano CAPONIGRO, « Introducing Headless Relative Clauses and the findings from Mesoamerican languages », in Ivano CAPONIGRO, Harold TORRENCE, Roberto ZAVALA MALDONADO (eds.), *Headless Relative Clauses in Mesoamerican Languages*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2021, p. 1-57.
- CITKO, 2004: Barbara CITKO, « On Headed, Headless, and Light-Headed Relatives », *Natural Language & Linguistic Theory*, 22, 1, p. 95-126.
- COMRIE and KUTEVA, 2013a: Bernard COMRIE, Tania KUTEVA, « Relativization on Subjects », in Matthew S. DRYER, Martin HASPELMATH (eds.), *The World Atlas of Language Structures Online*, Leipzig, 2013, online at <https://wals.info/chapter/122>.
- COMRIE and KUTEVA, 2013b: Bernard COMRIE, Tania KUTEVA, « Relativization Strategies », dans Matthew S. DRYER, Martin HASPELMATH (éd.), *The World Atlas of Language Structures Online*, Leipzig, 2013, online at <https://wals.info/chapter/s8>.
- DRYER, 2013: Matthew S. DRYER, « Order of Relative Clause and Noun », in Matthew S. DRYER, Martin HASPELMATH (eds.), *The World Atlas of Language Structures Online*, Leipzig, 2013, online at <https://wals.info/chapter/90>.
- EDIL, 2019: EDIL, « *An Electronic Dictionary of the Irish Language, based on the Contributions to a Dictionary of the Irish Language (Dublin: Royal Irish Academy, 1913-1976)* », 2019, online at <https://dil.ie/>.
- GARCÍA CASTILLERO, 2018: Carlos GARCÍA CASTILLERO, « The name and its circumstances: On the recognitional use of the Old Irish demonstrative *intí* », in José M. VALLEJO, Iván IGARTUA, Carlos GARCÍA CASTILLERO (eds.), *Studia Philologica et Diachronica in Honorem Joaquín Gorrochategui. Indoeuropaea et Palaeohispanica*, Anejos de Veleia Series minor 35, Vitoria-Gasteiz, 2018, p. 147-169.
- GARCÍA CASTILLERO, 2023: Carlos GARCÍA CASTILLERO, « On the NP syntax in the Old Irish glosses: The missing data of the isolated light-headed NPs », paper presented at the Workshop *Nominal Syntax in the Medieval and Early Modern Celtic Languages*, Göttingen, 27-28 October 2023.
- GRIFFITH and STIFTER, 2013: Aaron GRIFFITH, David STIFTER, *A dictionary of the Old-Irish glosses in the Milan Codex Ambrosianus C 301 inf*, 2013, online at <https://indogermanistik.univie.ac.at/milan-glosses/>.
- HASPELMATH, 1997: Martin HASPELMATH, *Indefinite Pronouns*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1997.
- HASPELMATH, 2013: Martin HASPELMATH, « Indefinite Pronouns », in Matthew S. DRYER, Martin HASPELMATH (eds.), *The World Atlas of Language Structures Online*, Leipzig, 2013, online at <https://wals.info/chapter/46>.

- MURPHY, 1952: Gerard MURPHY, « On the dates of two sources used in Thurneysen's Heldensage », *Ériu*, 16, p. 145-156.
- Ó CATHASAIGH, 1990: Tomás Ó CATHASAIGH, « On the Early-Irish prepositional relative without antecedent », *Celtica*, 21, p. 419-426.
- PEDERSEN, 1909: Holger PEDERSEN, *Vergleichende Grammatik der keltischen Sprachen*, 2 vols., Göttingen, Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1909.
- ROMA, 2007: Elisa ROMA, « Relativisation Strategies in Insular Celtic Languages: History and Contacts with English », in Paolo RAMAT, Elisa ROMA (eds.), *Europe and the Mediterranean as Linguistic Areas. Convergencies from a Historical and Typological Perspective*, Amsterdam, Benjamins, 2007 (Studies in Language Companion Series), p. 245-288.
- ROMA, 2009: Elisa ROMA, « How many definiteness markers per NP in Old Irish? », in Stefan ZIMMER (ed.), *Kelten am Rhein: Akten des dreizehnten Internationalen Keltologiekongresses, 23. bis 27. Juli 2007 in Bonn*, Mainz, Philipp von Zabern, 2009, p. 223-231.
- ROMA, 2014: Elisa ROMA, « Old Irish noun phrases: data from the Milan Glosses and a hypothesis for the origin of the single article constraint », in Elisa ROMA, David STIFTER (eds.), *Linguistic and philological studies in Early Irish*, Lewinston, NY, Edwin Mellen, 2014, p. 131-176.
- SADLER and CAMILLERI, 2018: Louisa SADLER and Maris CAMILLERI, « Free relatives in Maltese », *Brill's Journal of Afroasiatic Languages and Linguistics*, 10, p. 115-159.
- STIFTER *et alii*, 2021: David STIFTER, Bernhard BAUER, Elliott LASH, Fangzhe QIU, Nora WHITE, Siobhán BARRETT, Aaron GRIFFITH, Romanas BULATOVAS, Francesco FELICI, Ellen GANLY, Truc HA NGUYEN, Lars NOOII, *Corpus PalaeoHibernicum (CorPH) v1.0, 2021*, online at <https://chronhib.maynoothuniversity.ie/chronhibWebsite/home>.
- STOKES and STRACHAN, 1901 (*Thes.*): Whitley STOKES, John STRACHAN, *Thesaurus palaeohibernicus*, 2 vols., Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1901.
- THURNEYSEN, 1946 (GOI): Rudolf THURNEYSEN, *A grammar of Old Irish*, Translated from the German by D. A. Binchy and O. Bergin, Dublin, Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, 1946.